

8T – Matric Tensor Fluctuations and Initial Conditions of Manifolds

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Abstract:

By analyzing the 8T setting, a varying Lorentz manifold, which is confined in a manifold packet, alongside matric tensor fluctuations, it is possible to analyze the process in which new universe are born. In particular, it is possible to predict that the rate of time invariant acceleration will be dependent upon the initial conditions of the matric tensor that was departed from the original manifold.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matric tensor M , given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

If these two are hold to be true, we have areas of extremum curvature on the manifold and negative time invariant acceleration. The demand of extrunum curvature to stay as they are overtime means the acceleration cannot affect them – if so, directed away from them. This in agreement with what we speculate as "dark energy". Notice that M is now the matric tensor, g is the Ricci flow. That is the result of parametrizing the manifold to "s" variable and inserting it to EL operator, yielding agreement with Einstein principle of equivalence.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

We have presented the following arguments in previous papers. The first - in order of the universe packet to flatten each other the curvatures on the manifolds must be interfacing. That is synonymous with stating that the universe packet must have topologically invariant manifolds, or manifolds in which the extremum curvature distribution is identical on the matrix tensor. The second – each matrix tensor experience arbitrary amounts of fluctuations which could lead to a segment of the matrix to depart from the original, leading to additional element in the packet, which will get flattened by the other manifolds in the packet. We can consider the Multiverse has an infinite number of matrix tensor liars, to each liar there is an additional base liar, the Flow, which as finite sub covers of the entire matrix tensor that is compact spaces, given by extremum curvatures. We have presented the following visualizations in the 8T thesis.

each manifold, which flatten each other interact by the areas of extremum curvatures $\partial g / \partial t = 0$

The departing of each new manifold is unique and depend upon the initial conditions. that is to say that the fluctuations of each matric tensors leading to a new entity is unique. Some fluctuations could be more volatile than others leading to a bigger departing, or a segment of the matric tensor that is denser, leading to a more rapid acceleration in others. That is not contradiction to the fact that the actual rate of acceleration is invariant in each individual manifold. Another way to state it is the rate of acceleration is depended upon the shape and density of the departed segment of the matric tensor. That is not in contradiction to our framework nor it indicate that those universes obey distinct set of rules, but rather that no two universe could start the exact same way. That is of course also true regarding the temporal element, each manifold is being flattened in different time, each universe has a distinct age, some are colder and older than the others, that is given by the second representation of the main equation. Also in agreement with predictions of QFT regarding infinite amount of universes. The 8T most obvious way to regard each universe is as a thin liar confined within many other liars, interacting via areas of extremum curvatures, which stay as they are overtime, causing the liars themselves to accelerate and as a result get more flat and cold, all the universes according to the 8T has the same bosons, given by the primorial coupling constants series.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (1.31)$$

$$F_R \# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (1.32)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (1.33)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \quad (1.4)$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.41)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)